

Contrasting carbon dynamics in grazed and flood-prone grasslands on mineral and degraded peat soils

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ABSTRACT

Ecosystem-scale methane (CH₄) flux measurements from grazed grasslands remain scarce, despite their importance for understanding grassland contributions to the global carbon budget. In this study, we present full annual budgets of both carbon dioxide (CO₂) and CH₄ derived from eddy covariance measurements at two contrasting grazed grasslands: a floodplain grassland at Marchegg, Austria, and an intensively grazed pasture at Sherman Barn, California. By combining continuous, year-round observations of CO₂ and CH₄, this study provides a rare, comparative assessment of greenhouse gas dynamics across distinct climatic, hydrological, and management regimes. Our results highlight how environmental conditions, grazing intensity, and hydrology jointly regulate CO₂ exchange and CH₄ emissions, underscoring the importance of including methane alongside net ecosystem exchange when evaluating grassland carbon balances. At Marchegg, characterized by seasonal flooding and moderate horse grazing on mineral soils, the ecosystem acted as a weak carbon sink in 2024, with a GWP₁₀₀ of 42.2 ± 113.4 g CO₂ eq m⁻². Net CO₂ uptake (-27.3 ± 30.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) was partly offset by CH₄ emissions (1.6 ± 0.04 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹), which were strongly linked to soil moisture and inundation events. In contrast, Sherman Barn, a cattle pasture on degraded peat soils, was a consistent carbon source in 2019, with a GWP₁₀₀ of 567.6 ± 120.5 g CO₂ eq m⁻², associated with high ecosystem respiration during summer. The site released 125.3 ± 32.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ of CO₂ and 3 ± 0.06 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ of CH₄. Across both sites, net ecosystem exchange was primarily linked to photosynthetically active radiation and vegetation greenness, while CH₄ fluxes were related to soil moisture rather than grazing intensity. Flooding at Marchegg reduced CO₂ uptake but enhanced CH₄ emissions, highlighting the critical role of flood timing within the growing season. Moreover, inundation appeared to suppress the spread of invasive plant species, emphasizing the ecological value of dynamic hydrological regimes. Together, these findings reveal the complexity of grassland carbon budgets and the need for site-specific, year-round CO₂ and CH₄ monitoring to inform climate-adaptive management strategies.

1. Introduction

Grasslands are among the most extensive terrestrial ecosystems,

currently covering approximately 26% of the Earth's land surface (FAO, 2025; FAOSTAT, 2008; Jones et al., 2017) and play a central role in global food production, biodiversity conservation, and climate

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regulation. Despite their ecological and socioeconomic importance, large areas of grassland have been degraded through overgrazing, land-use change, desertification, and nutrient depletion, necessitating urgent restoration efforts (Bardgett et al., 2021; Joyce et al., 2016; Wick et al.; Zhang et al., 2025). Managed grasslands have been identified as a key area for environmentally sustainable management, offering a range of ecosystem services including forage production, habitat provision, and significant potential for carbon (C) sequestration. (Follett and Kimble, 2000; Jérôme et al., 2014; Staerfl et al., 2012).

However, grasslands do not universally mitigate climate change. Their contribution to the global greenhouse gas (GHG) balance is highly variable, as they can function either as net sinks or net sources of GHGs, primarily carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), depending on environmental conditions, ecosystem processes, and land-use and management practices. (Cárdenas et al., 2022; Lal, 2004; Soussana et al., 2010; Xu and Baldocchi, 2004). Key abiotic drivers include temperature regimes, rainfall patterns, water balance, and seasonal phenology, and their functioning is further modulated by geographical context (temperate, tropical, alpine) as well as management practices. While long-term C flux research has traditionally focused on forest ecosystems, relatively few studies have investigated grassland C exchange across different climatic and geographical settings (Allard et al., 2007; Cárdenas et al., 2022; Gilmanov et al., 2007; Merbold et al., 2014; Soussana et al., 2010; Wohlfahrt et al., 2008). Besides the intensity of use, grasslands experience a wide range of site conditions and disturbances that significantly influence C fluxes. Their exchange is highly sensitive to disturbances like grazing and flooding (van Andel et al., 2012). Thus, grassland restoration and management practices, such as grazing optimization, hydrological restoration, fertilization, and increased plant functional diversity, are increasingly being explored for their potential to enhance both biodiversity, reduce spreading of neophytes, C sequestration and ecosystem functioning (Allard et al., 2007; Klumpp et al., 2011; Rutledge et al., 2017). To implement and adapt such management practices effectively, it is crucial to first understand the underlying ecosystem processes.

Moderate grazing, once naturally maintained by wild herbivores such as bison and horses, has been shown to stimulate plant productivity, biodiversity and enhance soil C inputs by promoting biomass turnover and root growth (Cárdenas et al., 2022; Soussana et al., 2010; Stoy et al., 2021). In recent years, the ecological role of large grazers has sparked discussions about rewilding efforts to restore ecosystem functionality in grasslands. However, modern livestock grazing introduces additional GHG emissions, as animals serve as mobile point sources of CO₂ and CH₄ via respiration, enteric fermentation, and excreta deposition (Cárdenas et al., 2022; Soussana et al., 2010). Moreover, the physical impacts of grazing, including trampling and selective foraging, can alter soil structure and microbial communities, influencing methanotrophic and methanogenic activity and thus affecting CH₄ exchange rates.

Natural disturbances, such as flooding when grassland is an integrated part of a floodplain, introduce further uncertainty to grassland C dynamics. Flood events can disrupt CO₂ uptake by limiting plant photosynthesis, particularly if occurring during peak growing periods, resulting in reduced net C sequestration (Lindenberger et al., 2025). Controversially, depending on the stage of the growing period, the additional moisture from flooding can enhance plant productivity. Additionally, the resulting anaerobic conditions favor methanogenesis, potentially converting grasslands into transient CH₄ sources (Laubach et al., 2024). Furthermore, the type of soil and its land use strongly shape C fluxes, since properties like moisture, pH, and nutrient content interact with management practices (e.g., grassland vs. forest), thereby determining the magnitude and direction of GHG emissions and uptake (Schauffler et al., 2010). The combined effects of management practices and episodic disturbances on different soil types complicate predictions of grassland C balance across spatial and temporal scales, underscoring the need for more empirical data, especially on CH₄ fluxes, which remain

underrepresented relative to CO₂.

Despite CH₄ being the second-most important anthropogenic GHG, contributing substantially to radiative forcing (IPCC, 2021), most C flux research in grasslands continues to focus predominantly on CO₂. This imbalance persists even though CH₄ has a global warming potential (GWP) 27 times greater than CO₂ over a 100-year period (IPCC, 2021). The complexity of CH₄ dynamics, regulated by variable soil moisture, oxygen availability, and microbial activity, makes it difficult to model and measure reliably (Schauffler et al., 2010). Furthermore, traditional static chamber techniques lack the temporal resolution to capture short-lived flux events, such as those triggered by grazing or rainfall (Mishurov and Kiely, 2011). The eddy covariance (EC) technique is a widely applied micrometeorological method for quantifying ecosystem-atmosphere exchanges of C and GHG. It provides continuous, high-frequency flux measurements at the ecosystem scale, making it more robust than plot-based or chamber approaches. A key advantage of EC is its ability to integrate the combined effects of multiple drivers, such as water table dynamics, flooding events, and vegetation growth, on ecosystem fluxes. By capturing these interconnected influences on C and GHG dynamics, EC offers a holistic perspective that supports the identification of key drivers, evaluation of ecosystem responses, and the development of targeted restoration or management strategies. In this sense, EC serves as a decision-support tool that links scientific monitoring with adaptive management in grassland and wetland systems. Furthermore, while modelling approaches can reliably estimate CO₂ fluxes under stable conditions, their accuracy decreases when disturbances occur, introducing uncertainties that highlight the need for in situ, high-resolution measurements using the EC method (Aires et al., 2008; Kirschbaum et al., 2015). Together, these insights indicate that incorporating disturbances into EC-based assessments is essential for accurately evaluating grassland C budgets and supporting restoration strategies. However, its application in grazed systems is challenged by the mobile and spatially heterogeneous nature of livestock emissions, which violate EC assumptions of steady-state, homogeneous flux conditions (Baldocchi, 2014; Coates et al., 2017; Stoy et al., 2021). In addition to the complication of mobile point sources, the accurate quantification of CH₄ fluxes remains challenging due to pronounced diurnal variations in boundary layer dynamics, as well as discrepancies between the spatial extents of flux and concentration footprints (Baldocchi et al., 2012).

Recent EC-based studies have begun to reveal how grazing intensity and timing affect GHG fluxes. Grazing can reduce CH₄ uptake due to soil compaction and altered microbial activity or increase CH₄ emissions via fecal deposition (Cárdenas et al., 2022; Soussana et al., 2010). However, these effects are highly context-dependent and often underreported, particularly in flood-prone or intermittently grazed systems.

Since agriculture accounts for 21–37% of total anthropogenic GHG emissions (IPCC, 2021), it is crucial to understand how grazing and various restoration management practices impact the C balance of grasslands. This knowledge is essential for formulating climate-resilient land-use strategies and achieving the 2°C goal of the Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015). Restoration measures must be evaluated not only for their enhancement of ecosystem services, such as flood mitigation, habitat provision, biodiversity increase and nutrient cycling, but also for their effects on biogeochemical integrity, including C sequestration and GHG flux regulation.

In this study, we present annual high-resolution CO₂ and CH₄ flux data derived from EC measurements at two grazed floodplain grasslands that share a flooding character but differ in soil properties and management practices: a moderately horse-grazed mineral soil grassland in Marchegg, Austria in 2024, and an intensively cattle-grazed degraded peat soil grassland with a deeper peat layer under a Mediterranean-type climate in California, United States in 2019. The deliberate contrast between a flooded mineral soil system and a drained, degraded peatland system reflects two widespread and globally relevant land-use types within managed grasslands. Degraded peatlands under agricultural use

represent a disproportionate source of GHG emissions worldwide due to enhanced soil carbon oxidation following drainage, while simultaneously being a focal target for restoration efforts aimed at climate mitigation. In Europe, this relevance is underscored by the EU Nature Restoration Law, which explicitly prioritizes peatland rewetting and restoration as a key strategy for reducing land-use-related GHG emissions.

Recognizing that soil effects are inherently intertwined with site-specific management and hydrological conditions, we compare the net C outcomes of these two contrasting soil–management–hydrology complexes to evaluate how inherent soil properties interact with management practices in shaping CO₂ and CH₄ balances. Understanding the drivers and dynamics of GHG fluxes in such systems is essential for informing evidence-based management and policy decisions, particularly in the context of peatland restoration, climate-adaptive grassland management, and the development of mitigation strategies under evolving regulatory frameworks.

We hypothesized that managed grasslands can act as net CO₂ sinks, but that flooding and grazing introduce episodic CH₄ emissions that may partially or fully offset these gains. Specifically, we expected that the flooded mineral-soil pasture at Marchegg would function as a net CO₂

sink with relatively moderate CH₄ emissions due to inundation events, whereas the drained, degraded peat soil system at Sherman Barn would exhibit higher net C emissions due to enhanced soil C oxidation and grazing intensity. Furthermore, we hypothesized that species-specific grazing behavior, soil substrate, and management intensity would differentially regulate CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes, resulting in contrasting GWP between the two sites. Our specific aims are to:

1. Quantify the C balance by incorporating CO₂ and unique CH₄ EC measurements of two contrasting grazed grasslands.
2. Identify key environmental drivers of C fluxes and evaluate their influence on temporal flux dynamics.
3. Assess the impact of management practices, including contrasting grazing regimes (moderate horse vs. intensive cattle grazing) and flooding as a natural disturbance, on CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes.
4. Evaluate how soil properties interact with management and hydrology to shape net CO₂ and CH₄ outcomes, informing climate-adaptive grassland management.

Fig. 1. Location of the two study sites in Marchegg, Austria and Sherman Barn, California, USA. The red dot marks the EC station.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study sites

To better understand C dynamics in grazed grassland ecosystems, particularly with respect to CO₂ and CH₄ exchange, we selected two ecologically distinct sites that provide rare long-term, ecosystem-scale CH₄ flux measurements in combination with continuous monitoring of grazing activity and natural disturbance events. The study sites comprise a restored floodplain pasture on mineral soil in Marchegg, Austria, and an intensively managed grassland on degraded peat soil at Sherman Barn, California, USA (Fig. 1). These two locations were chosen to represent contrasting but complementary end members of managed grassland systems: a seasonally flooded mineral-soil pasture with low-intensity horse grazing and a drained, organic-soil pasture under intensive cattle management. Despite differences in climate, vegetation, and grazing regime, both sites are characterized by strong anthropogenic influence and active management, making them suitable model systems for examining how soil type, hydrology, and management interact to regulate CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes across a broad range of environmental conditions. By comparing a flooded mineral soil system with a drained organic soil system, this study captures variability that is broadly relevant to grazed grasslands worldwide and allows for mechanistic insights that would not be accessible from a single-site analysis.

2.1.1. Marchegg, Austria

The Austrian study site is a floodplain grassland (48.2865, 16.9070; elevation 130.9 m), located in a 1,100-hectare nature reserve in Lower Austria, close to the town Marchegg. The grassland lies adjacent to the Morava River and is partially owned by the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF Austria), with the remainder owned by a private family. As a restored floodplain grassland, the site experiences periodic inundation due to natural reconstructions between the main river and nearby oxbow lakes, creating large temporary water bodies that drive anaerobic soil conditions and potential CH₄ emissions. The soil is characteristic of riparian environments, consisting of gleyed grey alluvial material with high water retention capacity.

An EC system, monitoring energy, water vapor, and C fluxes, including CH₄ and CO₂, was installed in October 2023 on a floating platform (built after the Treboň Ecosystem station, Czech Globe) to capture high-resolution CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes under these dynamic hydrological conditions. Grazing occurs year-round by a herd of free-ranging Konik horses, with a stocking density of 0.64 livestock units per hectare on open land and 0.27 livestock units per hectare across the entire area, including forested sections in 2024 (Westerhof et al., 2024), supplemented by additional seasonal cattle grazing. This grazing regime, combined with episodic flooding, presents a complex mosaic of biological and physical drivers influencing GHG fluxes, making it an ideal location to study interactive effects of management and natural disturbance.

2.1.2. Sherman Barn, California, USA

The second site, Sherman Barn (AmeriFlux: US-Snf), is located on Sherman Island in the Sacramento–San Joaquin Delta, California (38.0402, -121.7272; elevation -4 m). The deep peat soils of the Delta have been drained since the mid-19th century for agriculture, exposing the C-rich soils to oxygen (Deverel and Leighton, 2010). Since then, microbial oxidation combined with peat compaction has led to widespread land subsidence and an estimated loss of nearly 200 Tg of C (Drexler et al., 2009). Both agricultural and pasture soils in the Delta typically exhibit a mixed surface layer of degraded, oxidized peat and mineral soil, underlain by a deeper peat horizon. Sherman Barn pasture is a representative example of this mixed-soil ecosystem and is therefore classified here as a site with degraded peat soil. Prior land use included the cultivation of asparagus and corn. Today the site is managed by the California Department of Water Resources (DWR) and is characterized

by persistently high groundwater levels, which at times form surface ponds. Land use at the site is pasture with controlled livestock grazing (~5 head ha⁻¹ in 2019). An EC system monitoring energy, water vapor, and C fluxes, including CH₄ and CO₂, was in operation between 2018 and 2020. The predominance of grassland vegetation and differences in soil texture and organic matter provide a contrasting system for evaluating the influence of grazing on CH₄ and CO₂ fluxes under different climatic and soil conditions.

The meteorological conditions at the two study sites, Marchegg and Sherman Barn, were broadly similar in their study years (Fig. 2). In 2024, Marchegg recorded an annual temperature of 12.93 °C, while Sherman Barn's annual temperature was slightly higher at 15.08 °C in 2019. Annual precipitation was comparable between the sites, with Marchegg receiving 419.33 mm and Sherman Barn receiving 452.37 mm. However, Marchegg experienced additional flooding events mainly due to backwater effects from the Danube River, triggered by heavy rainfall in the upstream catchment area. The water level is expressed in millimeters below the ground surface. At Sherman Barn, the groundwater level remained unusually high for grassland due to its degraded peatland characteristics, occasionally resulting in ponding during winter and spring, but declining markedly in summer. In the summer the water level shows some sudden peaks, correlating with precipitation events. Since no direct water level measurements were available at the EC station in Marchegg prior to October 2024, we used data from the nearby gauging station at Baumgarten an der March (48.3021, 16.8819) as a proxy. From October 2024 onward, water level data collected directly at the EC station confirmed that both records exhibit nearly identical temporal patterns, reliably capturing the timing of flood events. It should be noted, however, that the Baumgarten site is located at a slightly higher elevation than the EC tower. As a result, groundwater levels recorded below the soil surface at Baumgarten can already correspond to surface flooding at the EC site. Despite this offset, the development and dynamics of water levels are consistent across both sites, with groundwater peaks in Baumgarten reliably indicating inundation events at Marchegg. Soil temperatures were generally slightly higher at Sherman Barn compared to Marchegg, with Marchegg showing stronger fluctuations. In Marchegg, soil moisture was more variable, while periods of drying followed by sharp increases after flooding events, with soil water content was significantly higher at Sherman Barn.

Table 1 summarizes the site characteristics of Marchegg and Sherman Barn.

2.2. Grassland management: Grazing and flooding

The floodplain grassland in Marchegg, Austria, is continuously grazed year-round by a herd of 24 Konik horses in 2024 on 80 ha, managed by WWF Austria (Westerhof et al., 2024). This management follows the "herbivore theory," which posits that large herbivores play a key ecological role in maintaining open grassland landscapes by suppressing woody plant encroachment, thereby preserving biodiversity and habitat structure. To evaluate the impact of grazing on GHG fluxes, the leading horse was equipped with a GPS tracker in 2024, recording its position every 20 min. GPS timestamps were rounded to the nearest half hour to match the EC flux intervals. A horse was defined as "present" for a given 30-minute flux period if at least one GPS fix occurred within that half-hour window and the corresponding location fell within the modeled EC footprint. The footprint was calculated following Kljun et al. (2015), and only data located in the upwind sector (±50° relative to wind direction) were considered. Flux measurements were therefore attributed to grazing influence only when this condition was met, ensuring that animal presence was conservatively linked to periods with potential direct impact on the EC signal (Supplementary A1).

Complementary to the year-round horse grazing, two short rotational cattle paddocks were introduced in 2024 as part of the reserve's adaptive management plan: (i) twelve cows with ten calves and one bull from 25 May to 3 June, and (ii) three cows with one bull from 24 June to

Fig. 2. Meteorological parameters like air temperature, precipitation, and soil parameters (soil temperature and soil water content), as well as the ground water level in mm below ground surface for the site in Marchegg (blue) in 2024 and Sherman Barn (black) in 2019.

Table 1

Site information about the two study sites Marchegg, Austria and Sherman Barn, California, US.

	Marchegg, Austria (2024)	Sherman Barn, California, USA (2019)
Latitude,	48.2865, 16.9097	38.0402, -121.7272
Longitude		
Elevation (m)	130	-4
Annual temp (°C)	12.93	15.08
Annual precipitation (mm)	419.33	452.37
Soil type	mineral	Degraded organic peat
Management	Moderate Horse grazing, short periods of cattle grazing	Year-round extensive cattle grazing
Livestock units (ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)	0.64 (open land)0.27 (whole area with forest) (Westerhof et al., 2024)	~5
Grazing periods	Horse: all year; Cattle: 25.05 – 03.06.: 12 cows,10 calves, 1 bull 24.06.-17.07.: 3 cows, 1 bull	All year cattle grazing
Hydrological disturbances	flooding	High groundwater table
Flooding periods	01.01.-22.03.: flooded, 04.-13.06.: 2 m flood, 02.-05.07.: 0.5 m flood,14.-29.09.: 4 m flood	-

17 July (Table 1). Cattle were deliberately included in the management regime because, compared to horses, they are less selective grazers. This broader diet helps to suppress the spread of invasive plant species (neophytes), contributing to vegetation control and biodiversity goals of the restoration program. On the other hand, cattle produce more enteric CH₄ than horses, with default emission factors of 52 kg CH₄ head⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in Western Europe and 64 kg CH₄ head⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in North America, compared to 18 kg CH₄ head⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for horses, due to their ruminant

foregut fermentation system that favors methanogenesis, whereas horses rely on hindgut fermentation (IPCC, 2019). The area designated for cattle grazing exceeded the EC footprint, but the majority of their grazing zone overlapped with it. However, as the cattle were not tracked individually, it was not possible to determine precisely when they were located within the EC footprint and specifically in the upwind direction.

Grassland restoration at Marchegg has centered on hydrological reconnection: former oxbow lakes were reopened to the Morava River, allowing natural inundation to be part of the functioning ecosystem and to reshape soil structure and nutrient and C cycling. In 2024, a particularly wet year, this intervention resulted in prolonged and repeated flooding. The EC tower platform was floating continuously from 1 January to 22 March, with four distinct peak stages during that period, followed by additional high-water events in early June (4–13 June, ≈ 2 m depth), early July (2–5 July, minor overtopping), and mid-September (14–29 September, ≈ 4 m depth) (Table 1). Large standing water bodies persisted across the footprint well beyond each flood crest. These hydrological pulses, combined with the variable presence of horses and cattle, created a mosaic of management and disturbance conditions that is ideal for testing how restoration practices modulate CO₂ uptake and CH₄ emissions in floodplain grasslands.

At the Sherman Barn site, intensive cattle grazing is maintained year-round, with a consistent herd size of 100 cattle on the 20 ha plot. Unlike the GPS-monitored horse management in Marchegg, livestock presence at Sherman Barn was tracked using motion detectors installed to the EC tower to record the cattle presence when near the tower. In addition, phenocam was used for both phenology and recording timestamped images of cattle, allowing for visual counts and documentation of grazing activity. The motion detector data was aligned with EC flux measurements to help interpret short-term variability in CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes in relation to grazing pressure. Each movement near the detector was recorded and then movements were summarized for every 30 min for comparison with the 30-minute flux data.

Vegetation dynamics under grazing pressure were quantified using

the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). At the Marchegg site, NDVI was derived from Sentinel-2 imagery accessed via the Copernicus Browser, with a nominal 10-day revisit interval, subject to data gaps caused by cloud cover. At the Sherman Barn site, NDVI was primarily obtained from a phenocam, and Sentinel-2 data were additionally used for comparison.

2.3. GHG flux measurements and processing

Continuous measurements of ecosystem-atmosphere exchanges of CO₂, CH₄, H₂O, and energy were conducted using the EC method (Baldocchi et al., 1988). The EC technique quantifies vertical turbulent fluxes by correlating high-frequency fluctuations in vertical wind velocity with simultaneous fluctuations in gas concentrations, thereby providing direct, ecosystem-scale measurements of surface-atmosphere exchanges. Thus, open-path infrared gas analyzers (LI-7500DS for CO₂ and H₂O, and LI-7700 for CH₄; LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA) were paired with sonic anemometers (WindMaster, Gill Instruments Ltd., UK) to capture 3D wind vectors and the speed of sound at 20 Hz. All raw data was processed in Eddy Pro (version 7.0.9) using the express mode, with the default setting. Fluxes were computed as 30-minute covariances between vertical wind velocity and scalar concentrations, following standard processing protocols including coordinate rotation, time lag compensation, and spectral corrections (Detto et al., 2010; Hatala et al., 2012; Hemes et al., 2019; Knox et al., 2015). Double rotation of coordinate system was applied to align the mean wind streamlines so that cross-wind and vertical mean velocities were zero for each averaging period. To correct for air density fluctuations measured by the open-path CH₄ and CO₂ sensors, the Webb-Pearman-Leuning (WPL) correction was applied (Webb et al., 1980; Chamberlain et al., 2017). Half-hourly fluxes were filtered to exclude non-ideal conditions based on atmospheric stability, turbulence characteristics, friction velocity thresholds, wind direction, statistical outliers in mean densities and flux moments, and sensor window obstruction. The fluxes were cleaned using the standard cleaning plus REddyProc after Wutzler et al., (2018) with suffix `ustar_orig`. Quality assurance procedures were implemented to exclude data affected by inadequate turbulence (low friction velocity), unfavorable wind directions, signal artifacts, or poor sensor performance. Flux data failing criteria for atmospheric stability, variance thresholds, or statistical stationarity were removed from analysis. We applied the footprint model of Kljun et al., (2015) which uses a two-dimensional parameterization based on a backward Lagrangian stochastic particle dispersion model and has been successfully evaluated in previous studies (Dumortier et al., 2019). Assuming horizontally homogeneous turbulence, the measured vertical flux at sensor height was interpreted as the integrated contribution of upwind surface fluxes weighted by a footprint function specific to the measurement height. The model was implemented at a spatial resolution of 3 m, with the EC tower positioned at the grid origin, and footprint weights distributed across all grid cells to quantify their relative contributions to the observed fluxes. In Fig. 1 we show 2019 Sherman Barn and 2024 Marchegg daytime 80% footprint extent.

Gap-filling of missing or excluded half-hourly fluxes was performed using site-specific artificial neural networks (ANNs; Knox et al., 2015). The ANNs were trained using concurrent meteorological drivers including air temperature, soil temperature, net radiation and photosynthetic active radiation (PAR), vapor pressure deficit (VPD), water level, wind direction, and friction velocity (Eichelmann et al., 2018; Moffat et al., 2007; Papale et al., 2006). Missing meteorological data such as air and soil temperature, global radiation, precipitation and relative humidity in Marchegg site was filled with nearby weather station in Zwerndorf (16.83139, 48.33806; elevation 143.5 m). The ANN gap-filling and flux partitioning procedures were implemented using the local processing framework, with default parameter settings applied. Under these settings, a total of 800 ANN models were trained and evaluated per site and flux variable, resulting from the combination of

four candidate ANN architectures, 20 independent data extractions, and 10 random weight initializations per extraction. Of these, the 20 best-performing models were retained, and the median of their predictions was used for gap filling, thereby increasing robustness and reducing sensitivity to individual model realizations. To ensure representative model training across environmental conditions, clustering and random resampling were used to construct the training, validation, and testing datasets. Training, validation, and testing datasets were selected using k-means clustering to minimize seasonal and diel biases, implemented in MATLAB. Network architectures of increasing complexity were evaluated, and the simplest structure was retained when additional complexity reduced the mean standard error by less than 5% (Knox et al., 2015). The ANN training procedure was repeated 20 times, and the median prediction across the 20 ensemble members was used to gap-fill the annual flux time series. The available data were randomly divided into three subsets: two subsets were used for model training and validation, while the third subset was reserved for independent testing. During training, model performance was monitored against the validation dataset to prevent overfitting. Training was terminated when performance on the validation dataset no longer improved, indicating the onset of overfitting. Final model performance was then evaluated using the independent test dataset. Random initialization of network weights was applied to reduce the risk of convergence to local minima. This entire ANN training and selection procedure was repeated each time flux products were generated. More details about processing can be found at Knox et al., (2015) and Baldocchi et al., (2015). For CO₂ fluxes, the ANN models used the following environmental drivers: air temperature, PAR, VPD, air pressure, soil temperature, wind speed, wind direction, and seasonal indicators (sine and cosine of day of year). Seasonal indicators showed the highest relative importance (>15%), followed by soil temperature (~10%). Model performance for CO₂ gap filling resulted in R² values of 0.80 at Marchegg and 0.81 at Sherman. CH₄ fluxes were gap-filled using ANN framework but with the drivers air temperature, incoming shortwave radiation, wind speed, soil temperature, wind direction, and seasonal indicators (sine and cosine of day of year). Air temperature and the seasonal indicators showed the highest relative importance (>15%), while the remaining variables contributed less than 10% in the median model importance. Model performance for CH₄ gap filling was lower than for CO₂, with R² values of 0.50 at Marchegg and 0.24 at Sherman. The diagram of ANN gap-filling can be seen at Supplementary (Figure A2). Net ecosystem exchange (NEE) of CO₂ was partitioned into gross primary productivity (GPP) and ecosystem respiration (ER) using an ANN-based approach. Daytime ER was predicted from nighttime fluxes under the assumption of negligible photosynthetic activity, allowing GPP to be inferred as the difference between ER and NEE. By convention, negative NEE values represent net CO₂ uptake by the ecosystem.

The complete list of sensors used on both sites are presented in Table A1 in the supplementary.

2.4. Data analysis

The analysis is based on one full year of flux and meteorological measurements: 2019 at Sherman Barn and 2024 at Marchegg. All cumulative yearly sums refer to the respective study year, while daily sums were derived from the processed 30 min values. Data processing, visualization, and statistical analysis were conducted in python (Python 3.12.4 | packaged by Anaconda, Inc.).

2.4.1. Global Warming Potential

To compare the climate impact of CO₂ and CH₄ on a common scale, we calculated the GWP. This metric expresses the radiative forcing of a GHG relative to CO₂ over a defined time horizon. Following the IPCC AR6, CH₄ was assigned a GWP₁₀₀ factor of 27 and GWP₂₀ of 81 (IPCC, 2021). Thus, CH₄ fluxes were converted into CO₂ equivalents (CO₂ eq)

and combined with net CO₂ exchange to provide an integrated measure of the ecosystem's net climate impact. This approach highlights the disproportionate role of CH₄ emissions in determining the overall C balance of ecosystems, despite their comparatively smaller mass fluxes relative to CO₂. Uncertainty ranges for annual CO₂ and CH₄ budgets were estimated using a bootstrap resampling approach applied to gap-filled half-hourly fluxes, capturing sampling variability and random measurement uncertainty. Resulting uncertainties for the GWP were propagated linearly through molar mass conversions and subsequent GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀ scaling. In this study, nitrous oxide (N₂O) fluxes were not measured and therefore not included in the GWP estimates. Given the potential importance of N₂O emissions from drained and degraded peat soils, future work should aim to quantify N₂O alongside CO₂ and CH₄ to provide a more comprehensive assessment of ecosystem climate impacts.

2.4.2. Mutual information theory

Traditional spectral approaches for identifying flux drivers are limited by their assumption of linearity (Sturtevant et al., 2016), like the previously described Pearson correlation. To address this, wavelet analysis can be complemented with tools that are better suited to capture nonlinear and asynchronous dynamics. Information theory offers such a framework (Ruddell and Kumar, 2009; Sturtevant et al., 2016). Because nonlinear estimators often outperform linear ones, information-theoretic metrics that incorporate lag effects are particularly valuable for investigating biophysical controls on fluxes (Ruddell and Kumar, 2009; Sturtevant et al., 2016). Their robustness in handling nonlinearity and asynchrony has already enhanced our understanding of biosphere–atmosphere exchange sensitivities to climate variability (Kumar and Ruddell, 2010) and the timescales shaping wetland CH₄ dynamics (Sturtevant et al., 2016).

In this study, a Mutual information (MI)-theoretic approach was applied to account for potential collinearity and lag effects between NEE or CH₄ flux, and their drivers. MI has proven to be a powerful tool for detecting nonlinear, feedback-driven relationships in complex ecosystems (Chamberlain et al., 2020; Knox et al., 2018). As a non-parametric measure, MI can resolve interactions across multiple scales (Chamberlain et al., 2018; Knox et al., 2018; Sturtevant et al., 2016) by quantifying the average tendency of two variables, X and Y, to occur jointly (Fraser and Swinney, 1986). In practical terms, MI represents the amount of shared information between X and Y, i.e. the reduction in uncertainty of one variable given knowledge of the other (Chamberlain et al., 2020; Knox et al., 2021). Importantly, MI is a normalized indicator of statistical dependence that requires no assumptions about the functional form of the relationship (Liu et al., 2022).

$$H_x = - \sum p(x_t) \log_2 p(x_t) \quad (1)$$

where $p(x)$ is the marginal probability distribution of X and x_t represents the states of X across time t . MI was then computed from both the marginal and joint probability distributions of X and Y:

$$MI = \sum p(x_t, y_t) \log_2 [p(x_t, y_t) / (p(x_t)p(y_t))] \quad (2)$$

To estimate the probability distributions, continuous variables were discretized into 10 fixed-width histogram bins. This bin number provides sufficient resolution while maintaining statistical robustness, as demonstrated by Sturtevant et al. (2016) and Ruddell and Kumar (2009).

To compare MI across different NEE and CH₄ drivers, we applied a normalized form, termed synchronous MI (MI_{sync}):

$$MI_{sync} = MI / H_y \quad (3)$$

This measure describes the interaction between X and Y at the same time step. An additional advantage of MI lies in its ability to capture temporal direction (τ) in interactions (Liu et al., 2022). The maximum MI (MI_{max}) within a specified lag window is defined as:

$$MI_{max} = \max [MI_{sync}(\tau)] \quad (4)$$

A positive or negative τ characterizes the interaction as asynchronous, indicating whether Y leads or lags behind X. We selected a maximum lag window of ± 60 days to assess whether a potential driver (Y) leads or follows NEE or CH₄ flux (X), allowing us to capture seasonally relevant lag effects linked to vegetation dynamics, soil moisture persistence, and biogeochemical processes, as well as both immediate and delayed ecosystem responses to environmental forcing. The MI_{max} observed within this window, along with the corresponding lag day, was then recorded, which identifies the strongest interaction.

2.4.3. Structural equation model (SEM)

SEM was used to quantify the conditional associations between climate, soil, and vegetation variables and CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes while accounting for correlations among environmental drivers. SEM allows multiple regression relationships to be estimated simultaneously and avoids the assumption of independent predictors inherent in simple correlation analyses. Results are interpreted as conditional associations rather than causal effects.

All variables were standardized (z-score) prior to analysis to enable comparison of standardized path coefficients and to improve numerical stability given differing units and ranges. Only observed variables were included, and correlated drivers (e.g., air and soil temperature, radiation, soil moisture) were allowed to covary, reflecting their shared variability. Path coefficients therefore represent the unique effect of each driver on the flux, conditional on all other variables in the model.

The SEM was specified using lavaan-style syntax and fitted using maximum likelihood estimation (Oberski, 2014) as implemented in the Python package semopy (version 2.3.11). Model performance was evaluated using coefficients of determination (R²) for CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes, representing the proportion of variance explained by all incoming paths in the model.

2.4.4. Soil sampling and chemical analyses

At Marchegg, we collected soil samples in April 2024 from the upper 10 cm, with eight replicates taken around the EC station. Organic matter content (OM) was determined as the percentage of weight loss on ignition (450 °C, 6 h) from dried, powdered sediment. Subsequently, the samples were analyzed for total C, nitrogen (N), and their isotopic composition using a mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific Delta V) coupled to an elemental analyzer (FlashEA 1112, Thermo Electron Corporation) at the Center for Physical Sciences and Technology (Lithuania). As the Marchegg soils were mineral soils containing measurable amounts of inorganic C, the samples were acidified with 1 N HCl prior to analysis to remove carbonates and ensure that measured C represents organic C only. In contrast, the Sherman Barn soils were peat soils with high organic matter content. For this reason, acidification was not applied to Sherman Barn samples, and total C measured in these samples can be considered organic C. At Sherman Barn, we collected soil samples in August 2018 from the topsoil layer (0–10 cm). Ten samples were taken using sediment cores within the EC footprint area, spaced 3 m apart. Immediately after collection, the samples were sealed in bags, stored at 4 °C, and later air-dried at room temperature in the laboratory. The dried samples were sieved to 2 mm, and all visible roots were removed. The processed samples were then ground to a fine powder and analyzed in duplicate for total C and N using an elemental analyzer (CE Elantech, Lakewood, NJ, USA).

Soil chemical analysis quantified C percentage (C%), nitrogen percentage (N%) and C-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio of the soil. At Marchegg, eight soil samples collected in the vicinity of the EC tower showed a mean C% 5.5 ± 1.17 and a N% of 0.5 ± 0.08 , and a mean C/N ratio of 12.1 ± 0.75 . In contrast, Sherman Barn soils had a higher mean C% of 8.7 ± 0.27 , and N% of 0.6 ± 0.03 , and mean C/N ratio of 13.8 ± 0.37 .

2.4.5. Methodological caveats

Quantifying GHG fluxes in dynamic grassland systems using the EC technique presents several inherent uncertainties. While EC remains a widely accepted method for measuring ecosystem-scale fluxes of CO₂ and CH₄, its application in grazed environments, particularly those with point sources such as animals, requires careful interpretation of the results (Cárdenas et al., 2022; Soussana et al., 2010). One major source of uncertainty in this study arises from the spatiotemporal variability introduced by grazing animals. Animal presence was assessed using GPS tracking (Marchegg) and motion detectors (Sherman Barn), but the EC method cannot precisely partition direct animal emissions (e.g., enteric CH₄) from background soil or vegetation fluxes. Because EC fluxes represent 30-minute spatial averages over a dynamic footprint, short-lived or spatially localized emissions may be diluted or not fully resolved. In addition, EC theory assumes horizontal homogeneity within the footprint, an assumption that may be temporarily violated during flood events. Although vegetation composition at both sites is relatively homogeneous, microtopographic variability (e.g., more waterlogged patches) exists. These wetter areas are generally located farther from the tower in Sherman and, if influencing CH₄ exchange, would most likely contribute via advective transport, which was not explicitly quantified in this study. Furthermore, lateral advection of CH₄ from outside the immediate footprint, including emissions from livestock located beyond the main flux source area, may also influence measured fluxes, as discussed by Laubach et al. (2026). Consequently, animal-related effects are interpreted qualitatively rather than as direct emission estimates. Within the conservation equation framework, the total flux measured by EC reflects both the turbulent eddy flux and the integrated storage of gases below the sensor, so these brief animal-related spikes are superimposed on background fluxes and cannot be quantified separately (Baldocchi, 2003; Baldocchi et al., 2012). Uncertainties were derived by bootstrapping the gap-filled half-hourly fluxes expressed per timestep. This approach quantifies sampling variability and random measurement uncertainty but does not explicitly account for gap-filling model or u*-threshold uncertainty.

A key limitation of this study is its reliance on a two-site, single-year comparison, which constrains the extent to which the results can be generalized across years or regions. Grassland GHG fluxes exhibit pronounced inter-annual variability driven by climate extremes, hydrological anomalies, and phenological timing (Hörtnagl et al., 2018). Accordingly, the findings should be interpreted as site-specific snapshots rather than representative long-term means. Nevertheless, the two study sites span a broad range of hydrological, soil, and management conditions, capturing contrasting system states that are highly relevant for managed grasslands.

Furthermore, the study design constitutes a natural experiment, in which soil type, climate, hydrology, vegetation composition, and grazing regime co-vary between sites. As a result, the effects of individual factors, such as soil type or grazing intensity, cannot be isolated. Instead, the analysis compares the net C outcomes of two distinct

soil-management-hydrology complexes, rather than attributing observed differences to a single driver.

Finally, the statistical approaches employed, like MI, and SEM, quantify associations and conditional relationships among variables but do not establish causal mechanisms, particularly given the strong intercorrelation among environmental drivers.

3. Results

3.1. Carbon balance

The GWP analysis revealed contrasting roles of the two study sites in terms of their annual C balance (Fig. 3). The floodplain grassland at Marchegg functioned as a weak net C sink based on the mean estimate, with a GWP₁₀₀ of -42.2 ± 113.4 g CO_{2-eq} m⁻² yr⁻¹. This balance resulted from a CO₂ sink of -27.3 ± 30.1 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ and CH₄ emissions of 1.6 ± 0.04 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹. However, the relatively large uncertainty range indicates that, within the 95% confidence interval, the site could also represent a small net source. When applying the shorter-term GWP₂₀ metric, which gives greater weight to CH₄, Marchegg shifted to a slight net source of 73.3 ± 113.5 g CO_{2-eq} m⁻² yr⁻¹, highlighting the sensitivity of its climate balance to the chosen time horizon.

In contrast, the Sherman site acted clearly as a net C source under both metrics. The annual CO₂ emissions amounted to 125.3 ± 32.6 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, accompanied by CH₄ emissions of 3.0 ± 0.06 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, resulting in a GWP₁₀₀ of 567.6 ± 120.5 g CO_{2-eq} m⁻² yr⁻¹. Under GWP₂₀, the stronger weighting of CH₄ increased the total to 784.1 ± 120.7 g CO_{2-eq} m⁻² yr⁻¹.

3.1.1. CO₂ dynamics

The NEE in daily sums (g C m⁻² day⁻¹) and the yearly cumulative NEE (g C m⁻²) of the Marchegg floodplain grassland are shown for the year 2024, with shaded areas indicating flood periods (blue) and cattle grazing (yellow, Fig. 4a). Starting in winter, the fluxes are mainly positive, leading to net CO₂ emissions. From mid-April onwards, however, the ecosystem starts sequestering C, turning into a sink for CO₂ at the beginning of May. Furthermore, winter and early spring in 2024 were heavily influenced by inundation, with water constantly present in the study area. The four blue shaded areas from January to April indicate periods when the entire grassland was submerged, interspersed with large bodies of water. Throughout the year, the floodplain grassland acts as a CO₂ sink, sequestering -27.3 ± 30.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹. CO₂ sequestration is heavily influenced by flooding periods, while the presence of cows does not show any visible influence on the CO₂ flux. At the onset of June 2024, coinciding with the primary substantial flood following the winter inundation, the fluxes underwent a substantial decline in negativity, thereby disrupting C sequestration and resulting in minor net emissions during the period spanning June to July. The substantial flood that occurred in September, with levels reaching up to 4 m along site the EC system, and which resulted in extensive flooding across Central Europe,

Fig. 3. Summary of the C budget of Marchegg in 2024 and Sherman Barn in 2019.

Fig. 4. Daily NEE in g C m^{-2} (green) and cumulative NEE in g C m^{-2} (blue) of the floodplain grassland in Marchegg in the year 2024 (a) and for the intensive grazing grassland Sherman Barn in 2019 (b). The flooding in Marchegg is marked in blue shaded areas and the cattle appear in yellow.

did not exert the same effect on CO_2 uptake as the flood that occurred in June.

The daily NEE fluxes ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ day}^{-1}$) and cumulative NEE (g C m^{-2}) for the intensively grazed grassland at Sherman Barn during 2019 are presented in Fig. 4b. The site commenced the year in a roughly CO_2 -neutral state, transitioning into a net C sink from mid-January onwards. It is evident that by early June, with a cumulative uptake exceeding -200 g C m^{-2} , the grassland functioned as a net CO_2 sink. Yet, even during this sink period, daily fluxes occasionally spiked to substantial emissions. In the second half of the year, this pattern reversed, and the site gradually transitioned into a net CO_2 source. By mid-November, cumulative emissions had surpassed uptake, resulting in a positive annual NEE of $125.3 \pm 32.2 \text{ g C m}^{-2}$, indicating a net release of CO_2 to the atmosphere over the full year.

3.1.2. CH_4 dynamics

The floodplain grassland in Marchegg functioned as a net source of CH_4 in 2024, with total annual emissions amounting to $1.6 \pm 0.04 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Fig. 5a). The dynamics of CH_4 flux were found to be predominantly influenced by flood events. The cumulative CH_4 flux curve demonstrated a consistent positive trend, with significant increases observed following periods of inundation, characterized by the presence of persistent surface water and anaerobic conditions within the EC footprint. The daily CH_4 flux shows increases of CH_4 emissions after the inundation events. It is noteworthy that the significant flood event in September 2024, accompanied by water levels rising to 4 m above ground, resulted in a substantial increase in CH_4 emissions. Conversely, no discernible alteration in CH_4 fluxes was evident during or following

periods of cattle grazing.

The intensively grazed grassland at Sherman Barn emitted a total of $3.0 \pm 0.06 \text{ g C m}^{-2}$ of CH_4 over the course of the year (Fig. 5b). The cumulative CH_4 flux exhibited a consistent and gradual increase over the course of the measurement period, devoid of any sudden fluctuations. Between June and September daily CH_4 emissions show an increase and starting November the daily CH_4 emissions decrease.

Fig. 6 presents the annual cumulative fluxes of NEE, GPP, and ER for Marchegg and Sherman Barn. Both GPP and ER reached higher values at Sherman Barn compared to Marchegg. In Marchegg, NEE was strongly influenced by flooding events (see Fig. 4 for details). At Sherman Barn, it is noteworthy that from June onward, ER exceeded GPP, causing the system to shift from a C sink to a C source (see Fig. 4 for further details). The influence of intensive grazing, flooding, and other potential GHG drivers on the GHG fluxes of these ecosystems is analyzed in more detail in the following sections.

3.2. Drivers of CO_2 and CH_4 fluxes

The relationship between NEE and CH_4 flux and their drivers differed between the two grassland sites, Marchegg and Sherman Barn, reflecting their distinct management regimes and site conditions. To account for temporal dependencies and collinearity among drivers, time-lagged mutual information metrics (MI_{sync} and MI_{max} ; Section 2.4.2) were applied, followed by SEM (Section 2.4.3) to quantify conditional associations among correlated drivers and GHG fluxes.

Fig. 5. Daily CH₄ flux in g C m⁻² (green) and cumulative CH₄ g C m⁻² (blue) of the floodplain grassland in Marchegg of the year 2024 (a) and for the intensive grazed grassland Sherman Barn in 2019 (b). The flooding in Marchegg is marked in blue shaded areas and the cattle appearance in yellow.

Fig. 6. Yearly cumulative NEE (green), GPP (blue) and ER (red) for Marchegg in 2024 (solid line) and Sherman Barn in 2019 (dashed line).

3.2.1. MI analysis

At Marchegg, NEE was most strongly associated with incoming

radiation and PAR, which exhibited the highest synchronous mutual information ($MI_{sync} > 0.6$; $p < 0.004$), identifying them as the dominant

controls on ecosystem CO₂ exchange (Fig. 7). Air temperature showed a moderate but significant association (MI_{sync} = 0.38). Soil temperature, soil moisture, and relative humidity exhibited higher MI_{sync} values than NDVI derived from Sentinel-2 imagery (~10-day resolution); however, these associations were not statistically significant. In contrast, NDVI showed a significant, albeit weaker, relationship with NEE. Maximum mutual information (MI_{max}) was also highest for radiation and PAR, with optimal time lags of approximately -2 days, indicating a near-synchronous response of NEE to radiative forcing. Horse presence showed no detectable influence on NEE.

At Sherman Barn, the availability of daily NDVI data revealed vegetation greenness as the strongest driver (MI_{sync} = 0.86, p < 0.001) of NEE (Fig. 7c), emphasizing the central role of canopy dynamics in regulating CO₂ uptake. PAR and global radiation were also important contributors. NDVI derived from Sentinel-2 showed weaker associations than daily phenocam NDVI, with similar magnitudes observed at both sites. Although cattle presence was explicitly included as a management-related driver, its synchronous MI with NEE was very low (MI_{sync} = 0.02), despite being statistically significant (p = 0.04), indicating a negligible contribution relative to environmental drivers.

In contrast to the NEE drivers, which have been shown to be associated with plant productivity (NDVI and PAR) at both sites, an analysis of CH₄ fluxes was conducted, which revealed that the environmental and management controls at the two sites differed (Fig. 8). At the Marchegg site, CH₄ emissions were strongly correlated with soil moisture and soil temperature (MI_{sync} ~ 0.5, p < 0.001), clearly separating this driver from all other variables except NDVI (MI_{sync} = 0.4, p < 0.001), followed

by air temperature (MI_{sync} = 0.32, p = 0.029). All other environmental variables, including relative humidity, radiation, and precipitation, as well as horse presence, exhibited weak and non-significant associations with CH₄ flux.

At Sherman Barn, CH₄ fluxes showed generally weak associations with all tested drivers. NDVI (sentinel2) displayed the highest MI_{sync} value, followed by water temperature (MI_{sync} ≈ 0.08), but these relationships were not statistically significant. Soil moisture and soil temperature were likewise non-significant. The strongest significant associations were observed for relative humidity and soil heat flux, though MI_{sync} values remained low (≤ 0.06). Overall, synchronous MI values for CH₄ at Sherman Barn were approximately an order of magnitude smaller than those at Marchegg, indicating fundamentally different levels of environmental coupling.

Detailed values of MI_{sync}, lag days, and the distributions of each driver, together with the corresponding scatterplots, are provided in Supplementary Figures A3 and A4.

3.2.2. SEM results

The SEM revealed distinct environmental controls on CO₂ (NEE) and CH₄ fluxes at the Marchegg site (Fig. 9a). For NEE, the strongest standardized associations were observed with PAR (-0.747, p < 0.001) and NDVI (-0.673, p < 0.001), both indicating increased CO₂ uptake under higher radiation and vegetation activity. PAR and NDVI were positively correlated (0.30, p < 0.001), reflecting their shared seasonal and phenological variability. Soil temperature showed a significant positive association with NEE (0.485, p < 0.001), whereas air temperature had

Fig. 7. MI_{sync} and MI_{max} for NEE in Marchegg (a-b) and Sherman Barn (c-d) for different environmental parameters. The p-value inside the bar gives the respective significance.

Fig. 8. MI_{sync} and MI_{max} for CH_4 in Marchegg (a-b) and Sherman Barn (c-d) for different environmental parameters. The p-value inside the bar gives the respective significance.

Fig. 9. SEM for Marchegg (a) and Sherman Barn (b), showing the direct and indirect effects of environmental parameters. The R^2 gives the degree of variation of the variable explained by all paths. Significance levels are: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$. Arrows thickness displays the strength of the relationship. The colors brown and blue represent positive and negative relationships, respectively. Relationships between the environmental parameters are in dotted arrows. TA: air temperature, TS: soil temperature, PAR: photosynthetic active radiation, SWC: soil water content, SHF: soil heat flux.

no significant association (-0.046 , $p = 0.52$). Soil temperature and air temperature were strongly correlated (0.918 , $p < 0.001$). Soil water content was significantly negatively associated with NEE (-0.209 , $p < 0.001$), indicating reduced net CO_2 uptake under wetter soil conditions.

For CH_4 fluxes, NDVI showed the strongest negative association (-0.512 , $p < 0.001$), followed by a positive association with soil water

content (0.392 , $p < 0.001$). These relationships indicate that vegetation activity and soil moisture were the dominant predictors of CH_4 variability in the SEM. Overall, the SEM explained 65% of the variance in NEE ($R^2 = 0.65$) and 43% of the variance in CH_4 fluxes ($R^2 = 0.43$).

At the Sherman site, the SEM identified vegetation activity as the dominant control on CO_2 exchange (Fig. 9b). NDVI showed a strong negative association with NEE (-0.794 , $p < 0.001$), indicating

enhanced CO₂ uptake with increasing vegetation greenness. PAR was also negatively associated with NEE (-0.195 , $p < 0.001$), although its effect was substantially weaker than that of NDVI. NDVI and PAR were strongly positively correlated (0.962 , $p < 0.001$), reflecting closely coupled seasonal dynamics. Both air temperature (0.106 , $p < 0.001$) and soil temperature (0.207 , $p < 0.001$) were significantly positively associated with NEE. Air temperature and soil temperature were strongly correlated (0.811 , $p < 0.001$), indicating shared variability in thermal conditions.

For CH₄ fluxes, air temperature and soil temperature exhibited opposing conditional associations. Air temperature was positively associated with CH₄ fluxes, whereas soil temperature was negatively associated. Soil water content showed no significant direct association with CH₄ fluxes, while water level had a small but significant negative association (-0.072 , $p < 0.05$). SWC and water level were positively correlated (0.648 , $p < 0.001$). The SEM explained 86% of the variance in NEE ($R^2 = 0.86$) and 8% of the variance in CH₄ fluxes ($R^2 = 0.08$). The low explanatory power for CH₄ is consistent with the approximately tenfold lower MI_{sync} values, indicating weaker and more variable controls on methane emissions compared to CO₂ exchange.

To further examine if NEE and CH₄ are driven from the same drivers and change simultaneously, the rate of change (dC/dt) was calculated for both NEE and CH₄. This allowed us to assess whether variations in these fluxes occurred simultaneously and to explore potential environmental drivers underlying the observed patterns (Supplementary Figure A5).

3.2.3. Management influence

The management of the two sites has proven to be divergent. While the Marchegg site has been subject to natural flooding as a result of restoration measures and moderate horse grazing, the grassland at Sherman Barn has been extensively impacted by cattle grazing. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the grassland floodplain site in Marchegg experienced greater impacts on the CH₄ flux from regular flooding compared to the effects of animal grazing in 2024. To better understand the influence of flooding events on CH₄ flux, the effects of both the winter flood and the substantial September flood were analyzed in detail. Fig. 10 a presents the relationship between time elapsed since the winter flood (left panel) and the September flood (right panel) and their respective impacts on CH₄ emissions. The trend lines, shown in red, indicate a significant increase in CH₄ emissions following both flooding events. The coefficient of determination (R^2) values were 0.18 for the winter flood and 0.28 for the September flood, suggesting a moderate correlation. The slopes of the trend lines were 0.76 and 1.29, respectively, highlighting a measurable rise in CH₄ emissions as time progressed after the flooding periods. Fig. 10 b compares the average daily course of CH₄ before and after the flood in September, showing a significant rise in the average CH₄ emissions during 24 h. The range of average CH₄ emissions before the flood was between -1 – $5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$

and between 11 and $21 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ after the flood in September 2024.

Given the small observed association between CH₄ flux and cattle presence in Sherman Barn, targeted analyses were undertaken to quantify the role of livestock management in CH₄ dynamics. At Sherman Barn, cattle activity within the flux footprint was tracked using motion detectors, enabling a comparison of daily CH₄ emissions under varying grazing intensities. In contrast, at the Marchegg floodplain grassland, GPS collar data for horses and farm records for cattle were used to identify animal presence periods.

At Marchegg, a linear regression analysis between daily cumulative CH₄ flux and horse presence revealed no significant correlation ($R^2 = 0.01$), suggesting that emissions were primarily governed by environmental drivers—especially flooding-induced anaerobic conditions—rather than grazing from the relatively small number of horses present annually. This finding serves to reinforce the preceding analysis, which posited that the dynamics of CH₄ at this particular site are predominantly influenced by environmental factors such as flooding and anaerobic soil processes, rather than by the grazing activities of the relatively limited number of horses present during the year.

By contrast, at Sherman Barn, CH₄ emissions remained consistently positive throughout the year, peaking during the summer months (June–September) when both microbial activity and grazing intensity were elevated. A linear regression between daily cumulative CH₄ flux and cattle presence count (Fig. 11 a) yielded a moderate positive correlation ($R^2 = 0.19$), indicating that increased livestock activity was associated with higher CH₄ emissions. While the coefficient of determination suggests that additional environmental and microbial processes also play a substantial role, the relationship supports the interpretation of cattle as mobile, spatially variable CH₄ sources within the grazed pasture. This link between emissions and animal activity underscores the relevance of grazing management in mitigating site-level CH₄ fluxes.

Fig. 11 b illustrates a comparison between a week with low cattle presence and a subsequent week with high cattle presence. The low-cattle week, spanning 17.03.2019 until 23.03.2019, exhibited an average daily CH₄ emission of $5.9 \pm 7.5 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (calculated from the daily mean of 30-min flux values). In contrast, the high-cattle week (24.03.2019 –30.03.2019) showed a higher average daily CH₄ emission of $8.1 \pm 12.4 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, highlighting the influence of grazing intensity on CH₄ fluxes. The plot shows the daily mean CH₄ flux for each week, with point colors representing the total daily cattle presence. Except for Day 6, all days in the high-cattle week had significantly higher cattle counts compared to the low-cattle week. Correspondingly, CH₄ fluxes were significantly higher on Days 2–5 during the high-cattle week.

Fig. 10. CH₄ flux over time after the winter flood (left) and the September flood (right) in 2024 (a). Both reveal a significant rise in CH₄ emissions. Daily average course of CH₄ emissions in Marchegg before the flood and after the flood in September 2024 reaching up to 4 m water level (b).

Fig. 11. Linear regression of the daily Sherman Barn CH₄ sum versus the cattle count on that day (a). CH₄ comparison of a week with low cattle presence (cross) and a week with high cattle presence (point) at Sherman Barn (b). The colorbar gives the daily sum of the cattle presence in the footprint at each day.

4. Discussion

4.1. Carbon balance and environmental controls

At the ecosystem scale, grasslands can act as either net C sinks or sources, largely depending on site-specific biophysical factors such as climate, soil parameters, physiological ecology and hydrology, vegetation structure and function, and land-use intensity (Blanco et al., 2023; Flanagan et al., 2002; Xu and Baldocchi, 2004). This study compares C dynamics at two ecologically and geographically distinct grasslands: the floodplain grassland in Marchegg, Austria on mineral soil, and the intensively grazed pasture at Sherman Barn, California on degraded peat soil. Despite their shared classification as grasslands, the two systems exhibited contrasting C balances shaped by hydrological regimes, grazing management, and environmental drivers. A strength of this study is its integrated approach, combining EC with animal tracking, vegetation monitoring, and soil measurements, which enables a more contextual interpretation of ecosystem-scale fluxes than flux data alone and covers a wide range of possible outcomes.

4.1.1. NEE and drivers

In 2024, the floodplain grassland at Marchegg acted as a modest net CO₂ sink (-27.3 ± 30.2 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹). This value lies at the lower end of reported NEE ranges for semi-natural European grasslands (-13 to -464 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹; Soussana et al., 2007), indicating positive but limited C sequestration. Compared with more intensively managed systems, CO₂ uptake at Marchegg was smaller. For instance, Allard et al. (2007) reported annual CO₂ uptake of -97 and -75 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ under grazing pressure, while Rutledge et al. (2017) observed differences of up to -160 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ depending on species composition, and Merbold et al. (2014) reported -339 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ in an intensively grazed Swiss grassland following restoration. These differences likely reflect the potential for higher productivity and grazing-induced regrowth in managed systems. The most comparable site to Marchegg, in terms of management intensity and climate, is Bugac, Hungary, a semi-natural grassland with light grazing (0.19 – 0.34 head ha⁻¹), where annual C balances ranged between -13 and -125 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Soussana et al., 2007). Grazing intensity in Marchegg (LU for the whole area: 0.27 ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) falls within this range. At the continental scale, European grasslands are estimated to be a weak net C sink (-15 ± 7 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for 1961–2010; Chang et al., 2015), placing Marchegg well within expected bounds.

Reduced CO₂ uptake at Marchegg in 2024 coincided with flooding during the growing season, which likely constrained photosynthesis during peak productivity. Lindenberger et al. (2025) reported reduced CO₂ uptake during and following inundation. The June flood occurred during maximum plant activity, whereas a September flood had no detectable impact on CO₂ exchange, highlighting the importance of

seasonal timing for hydrological effects.

Comparisons with grasslands on organic and peat soils further underscore the strong influence of site conditions. For example, grasslands on drained peat soils in Germany exhibited highly variable but often substantial GHG budgets, averaging 29.2 ± 17.4 t CO_{2-eq} ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Tiemeyer et al., 2016), illustrating how soil type and hydrological status can fundamentally alter C balance outcomes relative to mineral-soil floodplain grasslands such as Marchegg.

In contrast, Sherman Barn on organic soil functioned as a net CO₂ source in 2019, exhibiting a positive annual NEE of $+125.3 \pm 32.2$ g C m⁻² yr⁻¹, consistent with Cárdenas et al. (2022), who reported that pasture grasslands can shift between acting as CO₂ sinks (up to -540 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) and sources (up to $+391$ g C m⁻² yr⁻¹) in two consecutive years, depending on interannual variability.

Both GPP and ER reached higher values at Sherman Barn compared to Marchegg. The elevated ER at Sherman Barn can be attributed to its higher C content in the soil, while the lower ER at Marchegg can reflect its mineral soil conditions (Jorgensen and Well, 1973; Wang et al., 2003). Differences in GPP between the sites may be explained by contrasting vegetation composition, geographical location, and radiation regimes. Notably, at Sherman Barn, when conditions became drier and hotter in June and the water table declined, ER exceeded GPP, turning the site into a net CO₂ source. This seasonal shift is linked to the drop in the water table, which exposes deeper peat layers to aerobic decomposition, thereby increasing ER. In contrast, during winter when the water table is higher, decomposition rate of the upper organic-rich layer is lower, leading to reduced ER and allowing Sherman Barn to act as a CO₂ sink. However, four distinct positive NEE spikes in winter (Fig. 4b) indicate temporary CO₂ emissions. These sudden emissions occur when the water level rises locally, creating anaerobic-saturated conditions in the upper soil layers, which can lead to pulses of CO₂ release, likely associated with microbial activity responding to transient oxygen availability and changes in soil respiration dynamics (Andrews et al., 2023; Manzoni et al., 2020). NDVI appeared to be a more dominant driver of NEE at Sherman Barn, although this may partly reflect differences in data resolution, as Sherman Barn provided daily NDVI observations, whereas at Marchegg NDVI was only available from Sentinel-2 imagery at ~ 10 -day intervals, with additional gaps due to cloud cover. It is likely that NDVI would also emerge as a stronger driver at Marchegg if daily values were available.

Across both sites, SEM results showed that CO₂ exchange was strongly associated with vegetation state and radiative forcing. NDVI and PAR exhibited strong conditional relationships with NEE, even after accounting for their shared seasonality, consistent with previous studies highlighting the central role of vegetation dynamics in regulating CO₂ uptake (Barneze et al., 2022; Kasak et al., 2026). Thermal controls differed between sites: soil temperature was more strongly linked to NEE at Marchegg, whereas air temperature did not, despite strong

covariance, indicating that subsurface thermal conditions more directly regulate ecosystem respiration and root activity, whereas both air and soil temperature showed conditional associations at Sherman, likely reflecting differences in canopy–atmosphere coupling and soil thermal regimes between sites. Soil moisture was negatively associated with NEE at Marchegg suggesting reduced net CO₂ uptake under wetter conditions, potentially due to oxygen limitation or physiological constraints, consistent with studies showing site-dependent and non-linear responses of CO₂ fluxes to water table depth (Tiemeyer et al., 2016). Together, these results align with earlier findings that CO₂ fluxes are often best constrained by temperature and vegetation properties rather than hydrology alone (Imer et al., 2013; Virkkala et al., 2024).

4.1.2. CH₄ fluxes and drivers

Since CH₄ flux measurements from grasslands using EC are still relatively scarce, there are few suitable datasets available for direct comparison. At Marchegg, annual CH₄ emissions ($1.6 \pm 0.04 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) were slightly higher than those reported for Bugac ($0.8\text{--}1.5 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$; Soussana et al., 2007), despite Marchegg functioning as a net CO₂ sink.

CH₄ fluxes were primarily associated with soil moisture, consistent with numerous studies identifying water availability as a key control on methanogenesis (Imer et al., 2013; Ojanen et al., 2010; Schaufler et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2025). The negative correlation with NDVI indicates that greater vegetation greenness was associated with reduced CH₄ emissions, likely reflecting enhanced plant-mediated oxygenation and diminished anaerobic conditions. These findings suggest that the wetter soils of the floodplain strongly promoted CH₄ production and release through anaerobic microbial activity. The elevated emissions observed in 2024 can be attributed to high soil moisture resulting from frequent flooding, consistent with the correlation analysis confirming soil moisture as the primary driver of CH₄ fluxes.

At Sherman Barn, the substantial CH₄ emissions of $3.0 \pm 0.06 \text{ g C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (equivalent to $+108 \text{ g CO}_{2\text{-eq}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) were lower than those reported for a nearby peatland pasture by Teh et al. (2011); $25.8 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$), but still contributed substantially to the site's net GHG source ($+567.6 \pm 120.5 \text{ g CO}_{2\text{-eq}} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

Seasonal increases in CH₄ emissions from June to September coincided with rising temperatures, while soil moisture remained relatively high, consistent with temperature-enhanced microbial activity under wet conditions (Feng et al., 2020; Yildiz et al., 2025). SEM revealed that methane dynamics were less well constrained than CO₂ exchange, particularly at Sherman Barn ($R^2 = 0.08$ vs. 0.86 for NEE). At Marchegg, CH₄ emissions were primarily associated with vegetation activity and soil moisture, consistent with hydrologically driven controls on anaerobic processes and plant-mediated methane dynamics reported across wetland ecosystems (McNicol et al., 2017; Virkkala et al., 2024). At Sherman Barn, CH₄ fluxes showed opposing conditional associations with air and soil temperature. Holding soil temperature constant, higher air temperature was associated with increased CH₄ emissions, likely reflecting enhanced near-surface transport or exchange processes. Conversely, higher soil temperature was associated with reduced CH₄ emissions when air temperature was held constant, coinciding with a strong negative correlation between soil temperature and soil water content, indicative of drier and more oxic soil conditions that suppress methanogenesis or enhance methane oxidation. The low explanatory power underscores the episodic, non-linear, and transport-influenced nature of CH₄ fluxes in managed peatland pastures. Baldocchi et al. (2012) highlight that interpreting CH₄ and other trace gas fluxes over complex managed landscapes is challenging due to spatial heterogeneity and environmental drivers, and by extension this underscores that variability in CO₂ exchange, including shifts between net source and sink behavior, is common and influenced by both biophysical and meteorological conditions even in ostensibly homogeneous pasture environments. CH₄ emissions from grassland pastures should be interpreted with caution, as measured fluxes may partly reflect advective transport

from external sources rather than local production, particularly in landscapes with nearby large cattle herds (Laubach et al., 2026).

4.1.3. Coupled CO₂–CH₄ dynamics and soil context

Across both sites, CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes were correlated, particularly early in the year, consistent with Rey-Sanchez et al. (2018). Later seasonal decoupling likely reflected site-specific disturbances: flood events at Marchegg and water-table drawdown at Sherman Barn altered CO₂ and CH₄ responses differently. These results highlight that the temporal relationship between CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes is strongly modulated by both hydrological dynamics and site-specific environmental drivers.

Soil C/N ratio is a key integrative indicator of organic matter quality and nutrient availability, and its interpretation is most meaningful when considered as part of the broader soil–hydrology–management system rather than as an isolated driver. In this study, differences in C/N ratio help contextualize the contrasting net C outcomes observed at the two sites, which represent distinct soil–management–hydrological complexes rather than controlled soil-type contrasts. At Marchegg, the floodplain grassland on mineral soil exhibited a relatively low C/N ratio, consistent with faster organic matter turnover and higher nitrogen availability. Within this system, such conditions can promote microbial respiration and CO₂ release under aerobic periods (Ammann et al., 2009; Blanco et al., 2023), while episodic flooding creates anaerobic conditions that favor CH₄ production, as reflected in the observed post-inundation emission pulses (Chamberlain et al., 2016). In contrast, Sherman Barn represents an intensively grazed pasture on drained organic soils with a higher C/N ratio, indicative of more recalcitrant organic matter and slower nutrient mineralization. We suspect that the oxidation of the highly organic soils at Sherman Barn played a role in driving this net C loss. However, rather than attributing flux differences solely to soil properties, the higher C/N ratio at Sherman Barn is interpreted as part of a coupled system in which soil legacy effects, persistent soil moisture, and grazing pressure jointly shape GHG flux dynamics. Within this context, slower decomposition may limit short-term CO₂ release, while sustained C availability under moist conditions supports continuous, albeit moderate, CH₄ emissions (Blanco et al., 2023). Taken together, these findings underscore that soil properties influence GHG fluxes through their interaction with hydrology and management, reinforcing the need to evaluate grassland C dynamics at the level of whole, site-specific systems when informing climate-adaptive management strategies.

During wetter conditions, the sustained availability of C substrates can facilitate CH₄ production over extended periods, although the magnitude of emissions at Sherman differs from those at Marchegg. At Sherman, soil moisture remains consistently higher than at Marchegg, and with higher temperature supporting continuous CH₄ emissions throughout the year. In contrast, Marchegg experiences pronounced wet–dry cycles driven by seasonal flooding and subsequent drawdown, which can trigger short-lived but intense CH₄ release events when anaerobic conditions and labile C availability coincide. This pulsed emission pattern contrasts with Sherman's more stable, lower-intensity fluxes. Notably, Scott et al. (2024) found that permanently inundated plots exhibited lower CH₄ emissions than sites undergoing wet–dry cycles.

4.1.4. Implications for grassland carbon management

Taken together, the results demonstrate that grassland C performance is fundamentally contingent on hydrological regime and soil type, with management acting as a modulating factor rather than a universal control lever. This differentiation has direct implications for GHG accounting under the Paris Agreement and reporting obligations within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change framework (UNFCCC, 2015). Current national inventories frequently apply aggregated emission factors to broad categories such as “managed grassland,” thereby masking the divergence between mineral floodplain systems and drained organic soils. The present findings support a shift

toward stratified emission factors that explicitly incorporate hydrological status, disturbances and soil type, particularly for degraded peatlands, which can act as chronic C sources.

The sink and source dynamics of grasslands must be interpreted in light of site-specific controls and uncertainties. At Marchegg, episodic flooding strongly influenced the annual balance by stimulating CH₄ emissions and temporarily reducing CO₂ uptake, making the moderate sink status sensitive to hydrological timing and year-specific conditions. In contrast, the persistent net source signal at Sherman appears primarily linked to degraded and drained organic soils and high water table, which promote sustained CO₂ emissions and CH₄ release. While inter-annual variability may alter the magnitude of these balances, hydrology at Marchegg and soil degradation at Sherman represent key structural drivers shaping their respective GHG dynamics.

The dual application of GWP₁₀₀ and GWP₂₀ (see Sections 2.4.1 and 3.1) further illustrates the importance of time-horizon choice in climate policy. While GWP₁₀₀ remains appropriate for long-term stabilization targets, GWP₂₀ exposes the short-term radiative forcing significance of episodic methane emissions (IPCC, 2021). In this context, the climate balance of the semi-natural floodplain grassland at Marchegg appears sensitive to both uncertainty and metric selection, with its classification shifting from a moderate sink under GWP₁₀₀ to a slight source under GWP₂₀. By contrast, the Sherman site consistently functions as a substantial net source across both time horizons, indicating a more robust and management-driven source signal. For flood-prone systems, this implies that restoration measures should aim not only at maximizing CO₂ uptake but also at minimizing the frequency and magnitude of anaerobic CH₄ pulses. For drained peat pastures, raising water tables and reducing grazing intensity emerge as priority interventions to curb sustained C losses. Such measures align with restoration-oriented regulatory instruments, including the EU Nature Restoration Law, which emphasize ecosystem recovery alongside climate mitigation.

Ultimately, the study underscores that effective grassland C management cannot rely on generalized sequestration assumptions. Instead, mitigation strategies must be site-adaptive, integrating hydrological restoration, soil-specific management, and multi-gas monitoring. Long-term EC observations provide the empirical foundation required to evaluate whether implemented measures genuinely shift systems from persistent source states toward verifiable climate benefits. Without such differentiation, policy targets risk overestimating the mitigation capacity of managed grasslands and underestimating the structural emissions from degraded organic soils.

4.2. Animal grazing effect on carbon dynamics

While environmental variables such as PAR and soil moisture were most strongly associated with GHG flux variability at both sites, grazing and land management practices appear to contribute to longer-term C dynamics in ways that are not always evident in short-term correlations. These management effects likely operate cumulatively and interact with vegetation structure, nutrient cycling, and disturbance regimes, rather than acting as dominant or independently quantifiable drivers at the temporal scale resolved by EC.

Previous studies have shown that more intensively managed grasslands often exhibit higher C retention than extensively grazed or unmanaged systems. For example, Ammann et al. (2009) reported that intensively managed Swiss grasslands functioned as net C sinks over a six-year period, whereas extensively managed plots experienced net C losses. Although cattle presence at the Sherman site was statistically significant in the SEM, the standardized effect size was very small (0.028), indicating a minor association with NEE relative to dominant environmental control. This pattern may be consistent with grazing-induced stimulation of plant regrowth or altered canopy structure, although the modest strength of the relationship indicates that grazing effects cannot be disentangled from concurrent environmental controls. At Sherman Barn, despite functioning as a net CO₂ source over

the study year under relatively intensive grazing (~5 head ha⁻¹), episodic periods of CO₂ uptake occurred under favorable conditions, such as during winter. Conversely, Marchegg, managed with low-density horse grazing (~0.3 head ha⁻¹), acted as a net CO₂ sink in 2024, though its performance appeared more sensitive to climatic variability due to limited management intervention. These contrasts align with earlier work showing that grazing can modulate both CO₂ uptake and ecosystem respiration, with net effects depending on intensity, timing, and environmental context (Peichl et al., 2012; Jérôme et al., 2014).

CO₂ fluxes thus appear to be indirectly linked to grazing through vegetation and soil disturbance or changes in productivity, whereas CH₄ fluxes are more directly associated with livestock presence. Ruminant livestock, particularly cattle, are known to emit substantially more CH₄ than horses due to differences in digestive physiology (IPCC, 2019). Default emission factors reported by the IPCC (2019) Refinement indicate enteric CH₄ emissions of approximately 52 kg CH₄ head⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for non-dairy cattle in Western Europe, compared to 18 kg CH₄ head⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for horses. These differences reflect fundamental contrasts between foregut fermentation in ruminants and hindgut fermentation in equines, where alternative microbial pathways limit methanogenesis.

At Sherman Barn, daily cumulative CH₄ fluxes showed a modest positive association with cattle presence (R² = 0.16), indicating that periods with more animals within the footprint tended to coincide with higher CH₄ emissions. These findings are consistent with (Klumpp et al., 2011), who reported that intensive management, including nitrogen input and frequent defoliation, enhances ecosystem respiration, particularly heterotrophic respiration fueled by rhizodeposition and decomposing roots. This relationship is consistent with contributions from enteric fermentation (IPCC, 2019) and potential soil disturbance effects that may enhance microbial CH₄ production (Rey-Sanchez et al., 2025). However, the relatively low explanatory power of this relationship, together with strong variability driven by environmental conditions, highlights the difficulty of isolating livestock-derived CH₄ signals using EC alone. Because cattle were often dispersed across the footprint and conditions can be windy, emissions were well-mixed in the atmosphere, likely minimizing localized disruption of EC measurements; small, transient increases in CH₄ were occasionally observed, consistent with findings reported by Baldocchi et al. (2012). Although pronounced emission peaks during weeks of high cattle presence suggest sensitivity of CH₄ fluxes to grazing intensity, these patterns should be interpreted as indicative associations rather than direct quantification of animal emissions.

The technical challenges of resolving grazing-related CH₄ emissions with EC are well documented. Accurate attribution depends on livestock remaining within the flux footprint, favorable atmospheric conditions, and detailed knowledge of animal movement (Coates et al., 2017; Prajapati and Santos, 2017). While EC systems can capture livestock emissions under controlled conditions, grazing systems with mobile animals introduce substantial uncertainty. Nevertheless, consistent with Weerasekara et al. (2024), our results suggest that grazing-related CH₄ signals can be detected at the field scale, albeit with considerable noise and limited precision.

From a management perspective, the findings imply that grazing intensity and timing may contribute to CH₄ dynamics, but environmental variability often outweighs grazing effects at short timescales. Moderate grazing has been shown to enhance C storage by sustaining productivity and biodiversity without degrading soil structure, whereas both abandonment and intensive use can reduce C sequestration potential (Soussana et al., 2010). Marchegg falls within this intermediate range and may benefit from low disturbance while maintaining biological activity. In addition, pasture composition plays an important role in C cycling; Rutledge et al. (2017) demonstrated that diverse swards can reduce C losses relative to monocultures, even without increasing productivity, suggesting potential mitigation pathways independent of grazing intensity.

Beyond flux dynamics, grazing at Marchegg also contributed to vegetation control by limiting the spread of neophytes such as *Symphotrichum lanceolatum*. Cattle, which exhibit less selective foraging behavior than horses, consume a broader range of plant species and thereby reduce the competitive advantage of invasive taxa. This indirect management effect may help stabilize plant community composition and ecosystem functioning, with potential implications for seasonal productivity and NEE.

Overall, while grazing presence exhibited weak daily correlations with CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes at both sites, cumulative management effects, including grazing intensity, species composition, and disturbance regimes, remain relevant for long-term C budgets. The evidence indicates that environmental drivers generally dominate short-term GHG variability, whereas grazing acts as a secondary, context-dependent contributor within a complex and noisy system. Grazing effects therefore cannot be interpreted in isolation from other disturbances, particularly hydrological events such as flooding, which similarly alter soil moisture, redox conditions, and substrate availability. The following section examines flooding as an additional management-relevant disturbance interacting with the environmental controls identified in Section 4.1.

4.3. Flooding effect on carbon dynamics

Flooding in Marchegg had a dual impact on ecosystem C dynamics, simultaneously stimulating CH₄ emissions and reducing CO₂ uptake. Elevated soil moisture following inundation created anaerobic conditions that significantly enhanced CH₄ release, particularly during wet–dry cycles that generated short-lived but intense emission pulses. Such episodic responses are consistent with observations from Chamberlain et al. (2016) and Scott et al. (2024), who reported that rewetting events can mobilize labile C in surface organic soils and promote methanogenesis more effectively than persistently saturated conditions, as also discussed by Hassett et al. (2024). These patterns suggest that the timing and dynamics of soil moisture fluctuations are important modifiers of CH₄ exchange in wet grassland systems. However, EC measurements quantify net ecosystem-scale CH₄ exchange, and the emission pulses observed therefore reflect integrated responses of multiple transport pathways rather than direct measurements of individual processes.

The June flooding event at Marchegg also coincided with a reduction in CO₂ uptake, reflected in less negative NEE during what likely represented a sensitive phase of plant development. Although increased precipitation can under some circumstances enhance gross primary productivity (Flanagan et al., 2002), the coincidence of inundation with the peak growing season in this case was associated with constrained photosynthetic activity and reduced C sequestration. Thus, rather than supporting productivity, the flood event in June hindered C sequestration, highlighting the importance of seasonal timing in determining hydrological impacts on grassland C dynamics. In contrast, a September flood had no detectable impact on CO₂ fluxes, underscoring the moderating role of plant phenology.

At Sherman Barn, flooding and surface ponding occurred primarily during winter periods characterized by high precipitation but low temperatures. Under these conditions, no pronounced increase in CH₄ emissions was observed immediately following inundation, consistent with temperature limitation of microbial activity. Koyama et al. (2024) demonstrated that local precipitation regimes and soil water conditions strongly influence the sensitivity of grassland CH₄ exchange, suggesting that both uptake and emission responses are highly site specific. Increased variability in soil moisture, as projected under future extremes of rainfall and drought, may therefore reduce the CH₄ sink capacity of some grasslands, although the magnitude and direction of these responses are likely to vary across ecosystems.

These observations highlight the importance of considering wet grasslands and managed pastures individually when assessing CH₄

dynamics, as wetland types differ substantially in their emission characteristics and controlling factors (Turetsky et al., 2014). From a broader management perspective, Joyce et al. (2016) emphasize the value of adaptive agri-environmental schemes that prioritize water retention, long-term monitoring, and the restoration of resilient wet grasslands as strategies to buffer climate impacts. Extreme meteorological events, including storms and floods, can also act as ecological disturbances that reshape vegetation dynamics, often favoring ruderal or disturbance-adapted species, while prolonged heatwaves and droughts may lead to drying of wet grasslands in some regions.

At the Marchegg site, the inundation period coincided with reduced establishment and spread of invasive neophytes, particularly *Symphotrichum lanceolatum*. Prolonged flooding likely created unfavorable conditions for germination and early growth of this species. By limiting neophyte expansion, inundation may indirectly support native plant communities and help maintain ecosystem structure, with potential implications for C flux dynamics. Dominance by invasive species has been associated with reduced biodiversity and altered canopy phenology, both of which can modify NEE by influencing photosynthetic capacity and respiration patterns. Thus, in addition to directly affecting CO₂ uptake and CH₄ emissions through altered photosynthesis and soil conditions, flooding indirectly shapes C cycling by regulating vegetation composition and limiting invasion pressure.

4.4. Uncertainty of the grassland greenhouse gas budget

The uncertainties outlined above have important implications for interpreting the observed C dynamics and their relevance for management. The EC method integrates fluxes over heterogeneous source areas, which is both a strength and a limitation in grazed systems. While it captures the net ecosystem response to grazing, hydrology, and climate, it cannot disentangle small-scale or short-duration processes, such as individual animal emissions or localized soil disturbances.

At both sites, animal presence introduced substantial spatiotemporal variability. At Marchegg, horse movements were recorded at 20-minute intervals, which may not fully capture rapid or transient animal activity within the EC footprint. At Sherman Barn, the presence of cattle was associated with increased CH₄ fluxes, but the EC method cannot resolve whether this signal originates from enteric emissions, manure deposition, trampling-induced soil changes, or their interaction. These limitations preclude precise source attribution and reinforce the qualitative nature of grazing-related interpretations.

The interpretation of environmental drivers is further complicated by collinearity and lagged effects. Soil moisture, temperature, radiation, and vegetation indices are tightly coupled, particularly in flood-prone systems, making it difficult to rank drivers unequivocally. Although MI and SEM help reveal dominant associations and temporal dependencies, they cannot fully disentangle cause–effect relationships. This is reflected in the low explanatory power of CH₄ models, particularly at Sherman Barn, where emissions appear more stochastic and influenced by unmeasured or unresolved processes.

The present analysis is based on one year of observations and therefore does not capture inter-annual variability, which is known to substantially influence annual GHG budgets through climate extremes, hydrological anomalies, and shifts in ecosystem drivers. While Marchegg was a very wet year in 2024, highlighting the hydrological management importance, it would be interesting to compare dry years in future studies. Sherman Barn was an average year in 2019.

Furthermore, the present study focuses on ecosystem-scale gaseous C exchange and does not quantify potential lateral C exports via dissolved organic carbon (DOC) leaching or changes in soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks. Thus, the reported budgets represent atmospheric C balances rather than a complete ecosystem C balance.

An additional source of uncertainty arises from the omission of N₂O fluxes. This is particularly consequential for the peat-influenced Sherman Barn site, where previous studies indicate substantial N₂O emission

potential (Kasak et al., 2021; Anthony and Silver, 2021, 2023). Managed peatland pastures similar to Sherman Barn have been shown to emit both CH₄ and N₂O at rates that contribute substantially to overall ecosystem global warming potential, with elevated non-CO₂ fluxes offsetting the “cooling” effect of photosynthesis (Teh et al., 2011). Consequently, the reported GWP in our study likely underestimates the total climate forcing of the system, reinforcing the need for multi-gas measurements in managed grasslands. While continuous N₂O monitoring was beyond the scope of this study due to its high cost, future efforts should integrate such measurements.

Taken together, these uncertainties reinforce a central conclusion of this study: grassland C dynamics cannot be reliably inferred from short-term observations, single drivers, or simplified modeling frameworks. The pronounced site-specific responses documented here demonstrate why broad generalizations regarding grazing effects or soil type are inherently limited and potentially misleading. Robust, management-relevant understanding of grassland GHG dynamics instead requires long-term, multi-gas EC measurements complemented by additional approaches such as chamber-based flux measurements, high-frequency animal tracking, and microbial or soil biogeochemical analyses.

Despite these constraints, a key strength of this study lies in its integrated methodological design. By combining year-round EC observations with independent data on animal presence (GPS tracking and motion sensors), vegetation dynamics (phenocam- and Sentinel-2-derived NDVI), and targeted soil characterization, we were able to interpret ecosystem-scale CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes within a well-defined ecological and management context. This multi-layered approach extends beyond flux measurements alone, enabling environmental drivers, management activities, and biogeochemical processes to be evaluated jointly rather than in isolation. Although causal attribution remains constrained by site complexity and intercorrelated drivers, the convergence of evidence across multiple data streams increases confidence in the observed patterns and provides a more holistic understanding of grassland C dynamics under real-world management conditions.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the C balance of managed grasslands is not an intrinsic ecosystem property but an emergent outcome of interacting hydrology, soil legacy, climate variability, and management intensity. The contrasting trajectories observed at Marchegg and Sherman Barn illustrate that grasslands can function either as net C sinks or persistent sources under contemporary management, depending on how biophysical constraints and land-use practices co-align. The decisive factor in this study is not grazing itself, but how grazing interacts with water regime and soil condition within a given climatic context.

These findings challenge generalized assumptions frequently embedded in mitigation narratives and inventory approaches that treat “grassland” as a homogeneous land-use category. The results show that degraded organic soils under intensive management can offset or even reverse potential sequestration gains, while periodically flooded mineral systems may retain net sink functionality despite episodic methane emissions. Thus, mitigation potential cannot be inferred from land cover alone; it must be evaluated through site-specific process understanding and multi-gas accounting.

From a policy perspective, this has three key implications. First, GHG inventories and mitigation strategies must explicitly differentiate grasslands according to hydrological status and soil type rather than applying uniform emission or sequestration factors. Second, adaptive management interventions, particularly grazing optimization and hydrological restoration, should be prioritized where they can shift systems away from persistent source dynamics. Third, long-term, multi-gas monitoring is indispensable for evaluating the climate effectiveness of restoration and management measures, especially under increasing climatic variability and extreme events.

By providing empirical, year-round CO₂ and CH₄ flux data across

fundamentally different grassland systems, this study contributes quantitative evidence necessary for improving national reporting frameworks and refining mitigation pathways under international climate commitments, including the Paris Agreement and regulatory instruments such as the EU Nature Restoration Law. More broadly, the results support a transition from generic sequestration targets toward site-adaptive, evidence-based governance of managed grasslands. Only by aligning management intensity with hydrological and edaphic realities can grasslands contribute reliably to long-term climate mitigation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Lindenberger: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Magdalena von der Thannen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hans Peter Rauch:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Dennis Baldocchi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Mihkel Pindus:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Data curation. **Daphne Szutu:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Joseph Verfaillie:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Kuno Kasak:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used DeepL and Academic AI from BOKU University based on ChatGPT in order to improve writing to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Anna Lindenberger, Magdalena von der Thannen, Hans Peter Rauch, Kuno Kasak, Mihkel Pindus reports financial support was provided by European Union. Kuno Kasak, Mihkel Pindus reports financial support was provided by Estonian Ministry of Education and Research. Dennis Baldocchi, Daphne Szutu, Joseph Verfaillie reports financial support was provided by Delta Stewardship Council, CA Department of Water Resources and the US Department of Energy Office of Science Ameriflux project. Reports a relationship with that includes: Has patent pending to. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.agee.2026.110531](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2026.110531).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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